

A CHALLENGING CASE OF GIANT FIBROID UTERUS IN A WOMAN WITH MITRAL VALVE REPLACEMENT & RECENT STROKE- A CASE REPORT

Samra Sahu¹, Yeshita V Pujar², Yuvarajkumar A Yadravi³, Farzana B Dharwad⁴,
Shruthi Andola⁵

*Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, KLE Academy of Higher Education and Research,
Deemed- to-be-University, Belagavi, Karnataka, India.*

Received: July 25, 2025

Accepted: Aug 20, 2025

Published: Aug 23, 2025

ABSTRACT:

Background: Uterine fibroid or leiomyoma is the commonest benign tumor affecting the female genital tract in the reproductive years with a prevalence of 20-40%. They are monoclonal tumors of the smooth muscle cells of myometrium.

Case presentation: A 48 year old perimenopausal woman presented with excessive menstrual bleeding for 7-8 months, with a prior history of Mitral valve replacement 4 years ago on anticoagulant therapy & a recent history of stroke 4 months prior to presentation at Gynaec department.

Result: The patient underwent Total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo oophorectomy under epidural anaesthesia with uneventful intra operative & post operative period.

Discussion: The case highlights the importance of multi disciplinary approach including gynecologist, physician, cardiologist, neurologist & anaesthetist for successful management of giant fibroid uterus.

Conclusion: Multidisciplinary approach, planning & pre operative optimization of high risk patients is cornerstone in preventing intra & post operative complications.

Keywords: fibroid, warfarin, stroke, mitral valve replacement

INTRODUCTION

Uterine fibroids or leiomyoma is a common benign tumor arising from myometrial fibre with higher prevalence of 20-40% in women of reproductive age (14-45 years). [1]. These tumors are usually asymptomatic and most of the time found incidentally during clinical examinations or during imaging [2]. When symptomatic it presents with excessive or unusual menstrual bleeding, bladder symptoms in form of frequent and urgent urination or urinary retention, bowel dysfunction, lower back pain, increased pelvic pressure, dyspareunia and Infertility. The first imaging modality preferred is ultrasonography [3].

The initial presentation, diagnostic problems and multidisciplinary therapeutic strategy used in a tertiary care hospital for a patient with a huge uterine fibroid are highlighted in this case report. This particular instance shows not only the clinical nuances associated with big fibroids but also the significance of multi modal management.

In this report, we are presenting the clinical details, radiological results, pre operative optimization, surgical procedure and postoperative treatment given.

CASE PRESENTATION:

A 48 year old perimenopausal woman, para 3 living 3 with prior 3 vaginal deliveries presented with regular excessive menstrual bleeding since 7-8 months associated with passage of clots & dysmenorrhea.

Past history-

Mitral valve replacement in 2021, on anti coagulation with Warfarin.

MCA infarct & left monoparesis 4 months back.

On examination, she had pallor, vitals stable, metallic click on CVS examination, normal vesicular breath sounds, irregular pelvic mass corresponding to 24 weeks gravid uterus size with restricted mobility, firm in consistency, upper & lateral borders well made out, lower border not made out, non tender.

Bimanual examination showed enlarged uterine mass corresponding to 24 weeks size with free & non tender fornices.

Her preliminary investigations revealed Hb of 9gm%, PT-INR of 7, LDH- 142

Ultrasound showed enlarged uterus measuring 8.1*13.5*13.5cms with 12.1*12*7 cms fundal fibroid & 7*6*5cms subserosal fibroid in right lateral wall. (Figure 1)

Warfarin dose was stepped down from 4mg to 2mg once daily & INR monitoring was continued until range was between 2.5-3.5.

MRI abdomen & pelvis was done which showed large fundal fibroid with cystic degeneration causing mass effect on adjacent pelvic structures (anteriorly on urinary bladder, antero superiorly indenting rectus abdominis, posteriorly on rectum & extending onto pre vertebral & presacral region, laterally reaching upto iliacus & obturator internus on left side causing compression of internal iliac vessels) with maintained fat planes.

She was planned for Total Abdominal hysterectomy with Bilateral salpingo oophorectomy.

Pre op optimisation plan-

Anemia was corrected by 2 pint PRBC transfusion.

Endometrial biopsy- no malignancy

Pap smear- negative for intra epithelial lesion

Physician, Cardiology & Neurology fitness was taken.

Anti platelet medication was stopped 5 days prior to surgery. Bridging anti coagulation was started 3 days prior to planned day of surgery. Warfarin was stopped & bridged with Unfractionated heparin 3500IU QID until 6hours before surgery.

On day of surgery, INR was 1.3

Intra operative-

Patient underwent Total Abdominal Hysterectomy with Bilateral salpingo oophorectomy under epidural anaesthesia.

Pfannensteil incision was taken, abdomen opened in layers, uterus exteriorised, irregular fundal fibroid & subserosal fibroid present (Figure 2 & 3)

Intra op blood loss was 100ml.

Prophylactic intraperitoneal drain was kept.

Abdomen closed in layers.

Specimen (Figure 4) weighed 2kg & was sent for histopathological examination.

Post op management-

Intravenous antibiotics given

Epidural analgesia continued for pain relief

Unfractionated heparin was restarted 12 hours post op.

Bridging with warfarin 4mg started 24hrs post op.

INR monitoring continued

UFH stopped on post op day 5.

INR was 2.7

Patient discharged in stable condition.

Sutures were removed on POD 10 during follow up visit.

Histopathology

Endometrium in proliferative phase

Subserosal, intramural & submucosal masses found- Leiomyomata

Cervix- chronic cervicitis

Bilateral ovaries & fallopian tubes normal

No evidence of atypia or malignancy in studied sections.

DISCUSSION

The incidence of uterine fibroids in reproductive age group ranges from 20-40% [1]. Risk factors include early menarche, late menopause, family history, obesity and nulliparity.

A recent survey carried out in the year 2018 showed that almost 17 women in every 1000 married women underwent hysterectomy every year in India because of fibroids [4,5].

Fibroids are benign monoclonal tumors that develop from the myometrium, or smooth muscle tissue of the uterus. Estrogen and progesterone are implicated in the genesis of fibroids [6]. Fibroids are uncommon in pre pubertal age; they are more common during reproductive age and they get regress in the post menopausal time. Estradiol is produced endogenously in fibroid tissue by the enzyme aromatase and fibroid cells express estrogen and progesterone receptors, which promote tumor growth when these hormones are present [7]. Based on location, uterine fibroids are classified as intramural (within the myometrium), subserosal (protruding from the uterine surface) and submucosal (within the uterine cavity) [8]. Uncommonly, fibroids may undergo degeneration like cystic, hyaline, or red degeneration.

These degenerative changes may manifest as severe pain due to a compromised blood flow.

The initial part of investigation is ultrasonography which gives reliable evidence and differentiates fibroid uterus from other pelvis masses. MRI pelvis is indicated for fibroid mapping. Diagnostic dilemma may sometimes arise in giant fibroids which then has to be differentiated from other pelvis masses especially ovarian tumors.

The influencing factors for treatment include number, size and location of fibroid, symptoms, age of patient, desire for future fertility [2].

Likewise, due to the giant size of the fibroid in the mentioned patient, the only treatment option was hysterectomy.

Management of such fibroids depends greatly on size and location, in this case the complexities associated with managing giant uterine fibroids, particularly as the patient had undergone Mitral Valve Replacement & was on anti coagulation and a recent history of stroke 4 months ago were rather challenging. The woman went through a number of years without the fibroids being diagnosed and hence the size of the fibroids increased to this extent.

Managing patients on anticoagulation and anti-aggregation therapy is a challenge for treating physicians. Stopping of therapy can increase the risk of thrombotic events during and after surgery. However, the non-interruption of these medications can increase the risk of bleeding during surgery and trigger a sequence of undesirable outcomes ranging from minor to uncontrolled bleeding. The optimal management of these patients is thus achieved through a balance between thromboembolic and bleeding risks. Several case-based considerations affect whether or not to interrupt anticoagulation or anti-aggregation therapy before surgery. These include evaluating an individual's underlying bleeding risk, the risk of bleeding associated with the surgical procedure, the timing of interruption and resumption of anticoagulation therapy. [9]

The patient was managed jointly by the team of Gynecologist, Physician, Cardiologist, Neurologist & Anaesthetist. Pre op optimization of INR was done by bridging anti coagulation. Close monitoring was carried out during intra op & post operative period and patient was discharged in stable condition.

CONCLUSION:

A challenging case of giant fibroid uterus in a woman with Mitral valve replacement on anti coagulation & with recent history of stroke could be successfully managed by multi disciplinary approach & pre op optimization in order to improve patient outcomes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

We thank Dr. Sooraj Patil (Neurologist), Dr. Prasad Raikar (Radiologist), Dr. Prasad M R (Cardiologist), Dr. Ravi Kerur (Anaesthetist) for their role in successful management of the case.

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Figure 1- Ultrasound image showing anterior wall fibroid

Figure1- Ultrasound showing Right lateral wall fibroid

Figure 1- ultrasound showing fundal fibroid

Figure 1- Ultrasound showing vascularity in fundal fibroid

Figure 2- Intra operative picture showing Giant fibroid uterus

Figure 3- Intra operative picture showing Giant fibroid uterus

Figure 4- post hysterectomy specimen (weighed 2kg)